

Incidence and Determinants of Incipient Diabetic Nephropathy

D.N. Parchwani, *D.D. Patel

Department of Biochemistry, Gujrat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj (Gujrat), *Department of Physiology, G.S.L. Medical College, Rajahmundry (A.P.)

(Received June, 2012)

(Accepted November, 2013)

Abstract:

Diabetic nephropathy is a late complication of diabetes mellitus. Microalbuminuria is considered to be an early sign of diabetic renal disease. It precedes persistent proteinuria and represents a potentially reversible stage of diabetic nephropathy. This cross-sectional analytical study was carried out on 180 type 2 and 145 type 1 diabetic patients. Patients having clinical albuminuria and with other causes of proteinuria were excluded. Microalbuminuria was observed in 34.48% patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM) and in 28.33% patients with type 2 DM. In logistic regression analysis, high HbA1c, and hypertension were strongly associated with increased albumin excretion in both types of diabetes mellitus. For type 1 DM, other independently associated factors, in order of importance were duration of disease, LDL-C and total cholesterol. Therefore, regular screening for microalbuminuria is recommended for all diabetic patients. Early screening for incipient diabetic nephropathy and aggressive management of these risk factors is important in optimising the renal outcome of patients with diabetes mellitus.

Key Words: Incipient diabetic nephropathy, risk factors, microalbuminuria.

Introduction:

Diabetic nephropathy has long been recognized as a major public health problem with far reaching consequences, not only for its adverse health impact on individuals, but also for its economic burden on the health care system and the society at large.¹ This complication is first manifested as an increase in urinary albumin excretion (microalbuminuria, a stage called incipient nephropathy) which progresses to overt albuminuria and then to renal failure.^{2,3} Detection of microalbuminuria is important from a clinical standpoint because, once detected, it is an indication for initiation of appropriate therapy for the purpose of preventing or delaying the advance of progressive diabetic nephropathy. Current recommendations from the American Diabetic association regarding screening for microalbuminuria suggest annual testing after duration of diabetes for 5 years.⁴ Recommendations include treatment with angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) with persistent elevations in urinary albumin excretion and no other recognized cause of kidney disease. It is important to assess factors related to the development of microalbuminuria in people with diabetes mellitus (DM) in order to identify whether such changes are due to underlying renal pathology or may be related to

functional changes. Keeping in view the paucity of data in India, this study was carried out to determine the prevalence of microalbuminuria among Type 1 and Type 2 diabetic patients and to assess the interrelation of microalbuminuria with basic patient socio-demographic features as well as clinical and biochemical parameters.

Material & Methods:

This study was designed to determine the prevalence of microalbuminuria and the associated risk factors in patients with diabetes mellitus. It was carried out from November, 2009 to September, 2011 after approval of institutional ethical committee. A total of 325 already diagnosed patients of varying age were enrolled for the study; out of which 145 (120 male & 25 females) were of type 1 & 180 (120 males & 60 females) were of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Patients with overt albuminuria, congestive cardiac failure, pre-existing macrovascular condition, urinary tract infection, pregnant females or patients who had given birth within the preceding six weeks and subjects showing disinterest were excluded from the study.

A detailed present and past history of each case was recorded including name, age, sex, address, religion, occupation, economic status, nutritional and personal habits, education, medication and history suggestive of any systemic illness. Weight (Kg) and height (meters) were measured using Omron digital body weight scale and wall mounted metal tapes respectively. Body Mass Index (BMI) was then

Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepak N. Parchwani, H.No. -B/10, New G.K. General Hospital, Gujrat Adani Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhuj (Gujrat)

Phone No.: +91 7600024672, +91 9426857672

E-mail: drdeepakparchwani@yahoo.com

calculated for each subject. A BMI less than 25 kg/m² was considered as normal, BMI between 25 kg/m² and 30 kg/m² as overweight and greater than 30kg/m² as obesity.⁵ All anthropomorphic measures reflect the average of two measurements (measured by the same person on the same instrument to avoid inter-instrument and interpersonal variation). Blood pressure (BP) was measured two times in the sitting position after 10 minutes of rest with a manual mercury sphygmomanometer and the two reading were averaged. Subjects were categorised for their blood pressure status according to the Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee (JNC 7).⁶ Hypertension stage 2 was defined with a systolic blood pressure equal to or exceeding 160 mmHg or diastolic BP equal to or exceeding 100 mmHg, and those who were in BP lowering medications. Normal blood pressure was considered to be a systolic < 140 mmHg and a diastolic as <90 mmHg. Readings between these levels were classified as stage 1 hypertension. Random urine specimens were collected from all participants at routine medical visits. The urinary albumin concentration was determined by Micral test using commercially available assay kits.⁷ The mean inter and intra-assay coefficients of variation were 3.6 and 4.4%, respectively. Normoalbuminuria was defined as Albumin Excretion Rate (AER) < 30 mg/24 hr, and Microalbuminuria as AER 30 to 300 mg/24 hr.⁸ Results were confirmed after 2 estimation measurements done in a space of 6 months. If the results of a 2nd estimation placed the patient in a different category from that based on the first estimation, a 3rd urine sample was obtained to confirm either the first or second estimation. After 12 hours of fasting, blood sample was collected for estimation of plasma glucose HbA1c, Serum cholesterol, serum triglycerides and high-density lipoprotein (HDL). Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol was calculated with Friedewald's formula. Adult Treatment Panel III (ATPIII) criteria was used to classify plasma lipid levels.⁹ Total cholesterol, triglyceride and LDL levels exceeding 200, 150, and 100 mg/dl respectively, and HDL levels below 45 mg/dl were considered as abnormal.

Data analyses was performed with the SPSS Version 15 statistical software. Two-group comparisons were made using *chi-square* (χ^2) for categorical variables and Student's *t-tests* or one-way ANOVA for continuous variables. For all analyses, the nominal level of statistical significance was <0.05.

Results:

Microalbuminuria was observed in 34.48% [95% confidence interval (CI), 27.6% - 39.2%] in patients with type 1 DM and 28.33% (95% CI, 26.2% - 34.1%) in patients with type 2 DM respectively. The trend was similar when the sexes were examined separately. In both types of diabetes, the prevalence of microalbuminuria rose progressively with increasing levels of fasting plasma glucose, HbA1c and hypertension status ($p < 0.0001$). There was also a progressive increase in the prevalence of microalbuminuria with increasing disease duration in type 1 DM patients only (Table I). However, no relation of microalbuminuria with age, gender, BMI, HDL-C levels, age at onset of DM, mode of treatment, socio-economic status and other lifestyle variations was found.

Table II and III depicts the selected characteristics among the study population with regard to normo albuminuria and microalbuminuria. In type 2 DM all of the variables (except HDL-C) were significantly higher in patients with microalbuminuria compared with patients with normal albumin excretion (Table II). However, for type 1 DM total cholesterol and HDL-C did not differ significantly between patients with normal and elevated albumin excretion (Table III).

Discussion:

This cross sectional study revealed a prevalence of microalbuminuria and its determinants among diabetic patients. The analysis showed an overall prevalence of microalbuminuria of 34.48% among type 1 patients and 28.33% among type 2 diabetic patients. The National Urban Diabetes survey¹⁰ showed the prevalence of diabetes in a population older than 40 years to be 23.8% in 6 cities of India, and the Chennai Urban Rural Epidemiology Study (2003-2004) estimated the prevalence in those older than 40 years to be 30.1%.¹¹ Several other epidemiological studies reported prevalence rates of microalbuminuria ranging from 7% to 42%.¹²⁻²¹ The variation in prevalence rates is most probably attributable to differences in design, setting, diagnostic criteria, methods for collection of urine, and its assessment of microalbuminuria and patient population.

In the present study, HbA1c, blood pressure and duration of diabetes (only in type I DM patients) were strongly associated with microalbuminuria, in accordance with other studies.^{17,22,25} Significant association was also observed when fasting plasma

Table I: Prevalence of microalbuminuria in diabetic patients with various variables.

	Type 2 DM*				Type 1 DM*			
	n	MAU [†] n(%)	χ ²	p	n	MAU [†] n(%)	χ ²	p
Gender								
Male	120	35(29.16)	0.123	0.726	102	37(36.27)	0.489	0.484
Female	60	16(26.66)			43	13(30.23)		
Age group(years)								
<20	12	1(8.3)			15	2(13.3)		
20-29	40	7(17.5)			39	10(25.6)		
30-39	48	12(25.0)	7.98	0.158	38	13(34.2)	8.45	0.133
40-49	62	20(37.8)			29	13(44.8)		
50-59	10	4(40.0)			15	7(46.6)		
≥60	8	4(50.0)			9	5(55.5)		
B.P.								
Normal	80	12(15)	22.2	<0.0001	59	10(16.9)	15.6	<0.0001
Stage 1 HTN	68	20(29.4)			58	24(41.3)		
Stage 2 HTN	32	19(59.3)			28	16(57.1)		
Glucose-F(mg/dl)				<0.0001				<0.0001
<110	33	4(12.1)	18.4		27	5(18.5)	23.5	
110-150	98	22(22.4)			76	18(23.6)		
>150	49	25(51.0)			42	27(64.2)		
HbA_{1c}				<0.0001				<0.0001
<8%	107	19(17.7)	15.9		81	15(18.5)	17.5	
8-10%	37	11(29.7)			37	18(48.6)		
>10%	36	21(58.3)			27	17(62.9)		
Duration of DM								<0.0001
<5 years	71	15(21.1)	4.87	0.088	51	7(13.7)	24.8	
5-10 years	67	19(28.4)			59	20(33.9)		
>10 years	42	17(40.5)			35	23(65.8)		
BMI								
<25	133	35(26.3)	1.69	0.430	114	37(32.5)	2.01	0.366
25-30	30	9(30.0)			22	8(36.4)		
>30	17	7(41.2)			9	5(55.5)		
Total Cholesterol(mg/dl)								
≤200	33	5(15.2)	3.46	0.063	58	13(22.4)	6.23	0.013
>200	147	46(31.3)			87	37(42.5)		
Triglyceride(mg/dl)								
≤150	24	3(12.5)	3.42	0.064	22	5(22.8)	1.59	0.208
>150	156	48(30.8)			123	45(36.6)		
LDL-C(mg/dl)								
≤100	41	7(17.0)	3.32	0.069	34	5(14.7)	7.69	0.006
>100	139	44(31.7)			111	45(40.5)		
HDL-C(mg/dl)								
≤45	108	30(27.9)	0.04	0.839	19	6(31.6)	0.08	0.775
>45	72	21(29.2)			126	44(34.9)		

*DM=Diabetes Mellitus, † =Microalbuminuria

glucose concentration was used in place of HbA_{1c}. It is established that once microalbuminuria is present, it is likely to progress to frank proteinuria over the next 5-10 years in 20 to 50% of subjects.²⁶ Microalbuminuria is also widely acknowledged as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease.²⁷ Similar to other studies^{28,29} this study confirms that microalbuminuria

is significantly associated with some adverse cardiovascular risk profile. The microalbuminuria positive group had a more deranged lipid profile with higher serum total cholesterol (only in Type 1DM patients), triglycerides, LDL cholesterol levels compared to the microalbuminuria negative group.

Some studies investigated the effect of gender on the incidence of albuminuria.^{13,30,31} Varghese et al

Table II: Selected characteristics of type 2 diabetic patients by urinary albumin concentration.

	Total Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus patients (n=145)			
	Normoalbuminuria (n=95)	Microalbuminuria(n=50)	t	p
Age(years)	39.6±7.3	45.6±6.8	4.8147	<0.0001
Duration of DM (years)	6.4±3.9	10.5±4.4	5.7541	<0.0001
BP-systole(mm/Hg)	126.4±20.2	140.8±18.8	4.1170	<0.0001
BP-diastole(mm/Hg)	82.6±8.2	86.6±7.9	2.8270	0.0054
BMI(kg/m ²)	22.1±3.3	23.6±4.6	2.2617	0.0252
Glucose-F(mg/dl)	134.5±20.6	174.2±24.2	10.3754	<0.0001
HbA1C (%)	7.8±1.6	9.0±1.8	4.1097	<0.0001
Total cholesterol(mg/dl)	212.3±34.7	220.5±30.2	1.4125	0.1600
Triglycerides(mg/dl)	176.7±62.3	210.6±60.1	3.1521	0.0020
HDL-C (mg/dl)	44.8±6.4	43.4±4.1	1.4016	0.1632
LDL-C (mg/dl)	109.2±32.3	146.3±30.4	6.7066	<0.0001

Table III: Selected characteristics of type 1 diabetic patients by urinary albumin concentration.

	Total Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus patients (n=145)			
	Normoalbuminuria (n=95)	Microalbuminuria(n=50)	t	p
Age(years)	39.6±7.3	45.6±6.8	4.8147	<0.0001
Duration of DM	6.4±3.9	10.5±4.4	5.7541	<0.0001
BP-systole(mm/Hg)	126.4±20.2	140.8±18.8	4.1170	<0.0001
BP-diastole(mm/Hg)	82.6±8.2	86.6±7.9	2.8270	0.0054
BMI(kg/m ²)	22.1±3.3	23.6±4.6	2.2617	0.0252
Glucose-F(mg/dl)	134.5±20.6	174.2±24.2	10.3754	<0.0001
HbA1C (%)	7.8±1.6	9.0±1.8	4.1097	<0.0001
Total cholesterol(mg/dl)	212.3±34.7	220.5±30.2	1.4125	0.1600
Triglycerides(mg/dl)	176.7±62.3	210.6±60.1	3.1521	0.0020
HDL-C (mg/dl)	44.8±6.4	43.4±4.1	1.4016	0.1632
LDL-C (mg/dl)	109.2±32.3	146.3±30.4	6.7066	<0.0001

reported that male sex was independently associated with microalbuminuria.³¹ In contrast, an association between sex and microalbuminuria could not be confirmed with the present study, even in univariate analysis. Similarly, no statistically significant relationship of microalbuminuria with age was found in the present study which is in accordance in the other studies. This was at variance with the findings of previous studies.^{22,24,31,33}

In the present study, patient with abnormal AER had longer known diabetes duration than those with normal AER 10.5±4.4 versus 6.4±3.9 years ($p<0.0001$) for type 1 DM and 10.7±4.2 versus 7.5±4.6 years ($p<0.0001$) for type 2 DM. Similar observation were made by other workers.^{13,34,38}

Elevated blood pressure is documented as one of the most significant factor in the pathogenesis and the progression of abnormal AER and eventually development of diabetic nephropathy in both type 1

and type 2 diabetic patients.^{17,28,39,41} Hypertension was also one of the major determinants of microalbuminuria in the present study. Univariate analysis revealed significantly higher levels of systolic and diastolic blood pressure in patients with microalbuminuria as compared with patients without microalbuminuria.

Nonetheless, this study has few limitations. Firstly, sampling may not be representative to all patients and/or the general population as undiagnosed subjects may have been excluded. Secondly, the design was cross-sectional and therefore, causal relationship cannot be ascertained. Thirdly, the proxy definition of diabetes mellitus was used in the study and auto antibodies screening such as Anti-GAD analyses was not assessed for patients. As such it is likely that some type 2 diabetes is misclassified as type 1. Other limitations include those inherent to patient reliability or compliance in complete urine collection.

Conclusion:

The prevalence rate of microalbuminuria was considerably high among diabetic patients, and is associated with many potentially modifiable risk factors. Patients and care providers should give the highest priority to improve glycaemic control sufficiently to maintain HbA_{1c} values below 8% along with other modifiable risk factors such as hypertension and lipid levels. If this can be achieved, the number of patients, in whom microalbuminuria develops, should decline. Therefore, regular screening for microalbuminuria is recommended for all diabetic patients. Early screening for incipient diabetic nephropathy and aggressive management of these risk factors is important in optimising the renal outcome of patients with diabetes mellitus.

References:

1. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H: Global prevalence of diabetes: estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030. *Diabetes Care*, 2004;27(5):1047-1053.
2. Mogensen CE, Christensen CK, Vittinghus E: The stages in diabetic renal disease: with emphasis on the stage of incipient diabetic nephropathy. *Diabetes*, 1983;32 (Suppl 2):64-78.
3. Sun YM, Su Y, Li J, Wang LF: Recent advances in understanding the biochemical and molecular mechanism of diabetic nephropathy. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 2013;433(4):359-361.
4. Donaghue KC, Chiarelli F, Trotta D, Allgrove J, Dahl-Jorgensen K: Microvascular and macrovascular complications. In: ISPAD clinical practice consensus guidelines 2006–2007. *Pediatr Diabetes*, 2007;8(3):163-170.
5. World health organization expert consultation: Appropriate body mass index for Asian populations and its implications for policy and intervention strategies. *Lancet*, 2004;363(9403):157-163
6. Chobanian AV, Bakris GL, Black HR, Cushman WC, Green LA, Izzo JL (Jr.), Jones DW, Materson BJ, Oparil S, Wright JT (Jr.), Roccella EJ: Seventh report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure. *Hypertension*. 2003;42(6):1206-1252.
7. Rodicio JL, Campo C, Ruilope LM: Microalbuminuria in essential hypertension. *Kidney Int*, 1998;54(568):551-554.
8. Molitch ME, DeFronzo RA, Franz MJ, Keane WF, Mogensen CE, Parving HH, Steffes MW: Nephropathy in diabetes: American Diabetes Association. *Diabetes Care*, 2004;27(suppl 1):S79-S83.
9. Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults: Executive summary of the third report of The National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP). Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III). *JAMA*, 2001;285(19):2486-2497.
10. Ramachandran A, Snehalatha C, Kapur A, Vijay V, Mohan V, Das AK, Rao PV, Yajnik CS, Prasanna Kumar KM, Nair JD: Diabetes Epidemiology Study Group in India (DESI): High prevalence of diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance in India: National Urban Diabetes Survey. *Diabetologia*, 2001;44(9):1094-1101.
11. Mohan V, Deepa M, Deepa R, Shanthirani CS, Farooq S, Ganesan A, Datta M: Secular trends in the prevalence of diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance in urban South India—the Chennai Urban Rural Epidemiology Study (CURES-17). *Diabetologia*, 2006;49(6):1175-1178.
12. Allawi J, Rao PV, Gilbert R, Scott G, Jarrett RJ, Keen H, Viberti GC, Mather HM: Microalbuminuria in NIDDM: Its prevalence in Indians compared with Europid patients. *Br Med J (Clin Res Ed)*, 1988;296(6620):462-464.
13. Alrawahi AH, Rizvi SGA, Al-Riyami D, Al-Anqoodi Z: Prevalence and Risk Factors of Diabetic Nephropathy in Omani Type 2 Diabetics in Al-Dakhiliyah Region. *Oman Med J*, 2012;27(3):212-216.
14. Chandie Shaw PK, Baboe F, van Es LA, van der Vijver JC, van de Ree MA, deJonge N, Rabelink TJ: South-Asian type 2 diabetic patients have higher incidence and faster progression of renal disease compared with Dutch-European diabetic patients. *Diabetes Care*, 2006;29(6):1383-1385.
15. Gupta DK, Verma LK, Khosla PK, Dash SC: The prevalence of microalbuminuria in diabetes : a study from north India. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*, 1991;12(2):125-128.
16. Gupta A, Gupta R, Sarna M, Rastogi S, Gupta VP, Kothari K: Prevalence of diabetes, impaired fasting glucose and insulin resistance syndrome in an urban Indian population. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*, 2003;61(1):69-76.
17. Jescic M, Sajic S, Jescic M, Kostic M, Peco-Antic A, Vujnovic Z, Necic S: Microalbuminuria in relation to metabolic control and blood pressure in adolescents with type 1 diabetes. *Arch Med Sci*, 2011;7(6):1037-1041.
18. Okpere AN, Anochie IC, Eke FU: Prevalence of microalbuminuria among secondary school children. *Afr Health Sci*, 2012;12(2):140-147.
19. Unnikrishnan RI, Rema M, Pradeepa R, Deepa M, Shanthirani CS, Deepa R, Mohan V: Prevalence and risk factors of diabetic nephropathy in an urban south Indian population: The Chennai Urban Rural & Epidemiology Study (CURES 45). *Diabetes Care*, 2007;30(8):2019-2024.
20. Venugopal S, Iyer UM: Risk Factor Analysis and Prevalence of Microalbuminuria among Type 2 Diabetes

- Mellitus Subjects: The Need for Screening and Monitoring Microalbumin. *Asian J Exp Bio Sci*. 2010;1(3):652-659.
22. O'Seaghdha CM, Hwang SJ, Upadhyay A, Meigs JB, Fox CS: Predictors of incident albuminuria in the Framingham Offspring cohort. *Am J Kidney Dis*, 2010;56(5):852-60.
 23. Vergouwe Y, Soedamah-Muthu SS, Zgibor J, Chaturvedi N, Forsblom C, Snell-Bergeon JK, Maahs DM, Groop PH, Rewers M, Orchard TJ, Fuller JH, Moons KJM: Progression to microalbuminuria in type 1 diabetes: development and validation of a prediction rule. *Diabetologia*, 2010;53(2):254-262.
 24. Viswanathan V, Tilak P, Kumpatla S: Risk factors associated with the development of overt nephropathy in type 2 diabetes patients: A 12 years observational study. *Indian J Med Res*, 2012;136(1):46-53.
 25. Xu J, Lee ET, Devereux RB, Umans JG, Bella JN, Shara NM, Yeh J, Fabsitz RR, Howard BV: A Longitudinal Study of Risk Factors for Incident Albuminuria in Diabetic American Indians: The Strong Heart Study. *Am J Kidney Dis*, 2008;51(3):415-424.
 26. Ritz E, Orth SR: Nephropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *NEngl J Med*, 1999;341(15):1127-1133.
 27. Obineche EN, Adem Abu: Update in Diabetic Nephropathy. *Int J Diabetes & Metabolism*, 2005;13(1):1-9.
 28. Mongkolsomlit S, Patumanond J, Tawichasri C, Komoltri C, Rawdaree P: Meta-regression of risk factors for microalbuminuria in type 2 diabetes. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health*, 2012;43(2):455-466.
 29. Toth PP, Simko RJ, Palli SR, Koselleck D, Quimbo RA, Cziraky MJ: The impact of serum lipids on risk for microangiopathy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*, 2012;11:109-118.
 30. Gall MA, Hougaard P, Borch-Johnsen K, Parving HH: Risk factors for development of incipient and overt diabetic nephropathy in patients with non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus: prospective, observational study. *BMJ*, 1997;314(7083):783-786.
 31. Varghese A, Deepa R, Rema M, Mohan V: Prevalence of microalbuminuria in type 2 diabetes mellitus at a diabetes center in southern India. *Postgrad Med J*, 2001;77(908):399-402.
 32. Sheikh SA, Baig JA, Iqbal T, Kazmi T, Baig M, Husain SS: Prevalence of microalbuminuria with relation to glycemic control in type-2 diabetic patients in Karachi. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*, 2009;21(3):83-86.
 33. Mehrdad S, Mohammad AA, Orafa AM: A study of the prevalence of micro & macro albuminuria in diabetic patients referring to diabetic center in YAZD. *J Shahid Sadoughi Univ Med Sci Health Services*, 2003;10(4 suppl):20-24.
 34. Adler AI, Stevens RJ, Manley SE, Bilous RW, Cull CA, Holman RR: Development and progression of nephropathy in type 2 diabetes: the United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS64). *Kidney Int*, 2003;63(1):225-232.
 35. Al-Salman RA, Al-Basri HA, Al-Sayyad AS, Hearnshaw HM: Prevalence and risk factors of albuminuria in Type 2 diabetes in Bahrain. *J Endocrinol Invest*, 2009;32(9):746-751.
 36. Mtiraoui N, Ezzidi I, Turki A, Chaieb M, Mahjoub T, Almawi WY: Renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system genotypes and haplotypes affect the susceptibility to nephropathy in type 2 diabetes patients. *J Renin Angiotensin-Aldosterone System*, 2011;12(4):572-580.
 37. Oue T, Namba M, Nakajima H, Ono A, Horikawa Y, Yamamoto K, Hamaguchi T, Fujino-Kurihara H, Yamasaki T, Tomita K, Miyagawa J, Hanafusa T, Matsuzawa Y: Risk factors for the progression of microalbuminuria in Japanese type 2 diabetic patients—a 10 year follow-up study. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*, 1999;46(1):47-55.
 38. Torffvit O, Agardh E, Agardh CD: Albuminuria and associated medical risk factors: a cross-sectional study in 451 type II diabetic patients. Part 2. *J Diabet Complications*, 1991;5(1):29-34.
 39. Mogensen CE: Microalbuminuria and hypertension with focus on type 1 and type 2 diabetes. *J Intern Med*, 2003;254(1):45-66.
 40. Schmitz A, Vaeth M, Mogensen CE: Systolic blood pressure relates to the rate of progression of albuminuria in NIDDM. *Diabetologia*, 1994;37(12):1251-1258.
 41. UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) X: Urinary albumin excretion over 3 years in diet-treated type 2, (non-insulin-dependent) diabetic patients, and association with hypertension, hyperglycaemia and hypertriglyceridaemia. *Diabetologia*, 1993;36(10):1021-1029.

Source of Support : Nil.

Conflict of Interest : None declared.